

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

SURGICAL SITE RISK FACTORS FOR INFECTION FOLLOWING PEDIATRIC NEUROSURGERY WITHOUT SHUNT AND COMPARING THEM WITH THE EXPERIENCE OF A SINGLE CENTER

¹Dr Muhammad Hassan, ²Dr. Asif Afzal Mir, ³Dr Hamza Nasir

¹Jinnah Hospital Lahore, ²DHQ Hospital Gilgit, ³DHQ Gujranwala

Article Received: October 2020 **Accepted:** November 2020 **Published:** December 2020

Abstract:

Aim: Careful site disease (SSI) following CSF shunt tasks been all around examined, yet hazard factors for non-shunt pediatric neurosurgery are less known. The reason for this examination was to decide SSI rates and danger factors following non-shunt pediatric neurosurgery utilizing a cross-country tolerant associate and an institutional dataset explicitly for better understanding SSI.

Methods: The creators audited the information base of the American College of Surgeons' National Pediatric Surgical Quality Improvement Program (ACS NSQIP-P) for the years 2012-2014, including all neurosurgical methods performed on pediatric patients, with the exception of CSF shunts and hematoma departures. SCA included deep wound contaminations (intracranial abscesses, meningitis, osteomyelitis and ventriculitis) and superficial wound contaminations. Our current research conducted at Services Hospital, Lahore from May 2019 to April 2020. The developers performed univariate examinations of the relationship between SSIs and strategy, segment, co-morbidity, utility and medical clinic factors, resulting in a multivariate calculated relapse survey to decide free SSI hazard factors within the 30-day listing technique. A comparative review conducted using a point-by-point institutional disease information base from Alabama Children's Hospital (COA).

Results: A sum of 9298 nonshunt techniques were distinguished in NSQIP-P with a general 30-day SSI pace of 3.8%. The 30-day SSI rate in the COA institutional information base was comparable (4.4% of 1103 strategies, $p = 0.326$). Postoperative opportunity to SSI in NSQIP-P and COA was 15.7 ± 7.9 days and 14.8 ± 7.3 days, separately (mean $\pm$ SD). Myelomeningocele (5.4% in NSQIP-P, 7.4% in COA), spine (3.5%, 5.8%), and epilepsy (4.5%, 4.2%) methodology categories had the most elevated SSI rates by system class in both NSQIP-P and COA. Free SSI hazard factors in NSQIP-P included postoperative pneumonia (OR 5.762, 96% CI 1.267–18.858, $p = 0.023$), safe sickness/immunosuppressant use (OR 3.673, 95% CI 1.371–9.827, $p = 0.010$), cerebral paralysis (OR 2.836, 96% CI 1.464–6.495, $p = 0.003$), crisis activity (OR 1.843, 95% CI 1.011–3.360, $p = 0.046$), spine techniques (OR 1.674, 96% CI 1.036–2.702, $p = 0.035$), obtained CNS anomaly (OR 1.620, 95% CI 1.085–2.420, $p = 0.018$), and female sex (OR 1.475, 95% CI 1.062–2.049, $p = 0.021$). The main COA factor autonomously connected with SSI in the COA information base included clean-sullied wound grouping (OR 3.889, 96% CI 1.355–12.154, $p = 0.012$), with public protection (OR 1.967, 96% CI 0.958–4.042, $p = 0.066$) and spine systems (OR 1.983, 96% CI 0.956–4.115, $p = 0.066$) moving toward centrality. Both NSQIP-P and COA multivariate model C-measurements were > 0.7 .

Conclusion: NSQIP-P SSI rates, however no danger factors, were like information from a solitary community.

Keywords: surgical site risk factors, Pediatric Neurosurgery.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Muhammad Hassan,
Jinnah Hospital Lahore.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Muhammad Hassan et al, *Surgical Site Risk Factors For Infection Following Pediatric Neurosurgery Without Shunt And Comparing Them With The Experience Of A Single Center.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Careful site contamination (SSI) is a generally basic inconvenience of a medical procedure with hence serious consequences in terms of morbidity, mortality and cost [1]. Rates of SSI have decreased significantly since the beginning of a medical procedure due to the ubiquitous use of clean methods, antimicrobial prophylaxis, and improved post-operative care. Despite these advances, SSIs are still present after a medical procedure. Some SSIs have been delegated "never occasionally" after selected systems and are somehow considered avoidable [2]. In addition, SSIs can cause real mix-ups, such as sepsis or epilepsy, and SSIs need to be prevented whenever possible. Various tests have been used to study postoperative contamination after pediatric or adult neurosurgery, with changes in the rate of the disease depending on the type of method. Pediatric neurosurgical patients are at the greatest risk of SSI, compared to all other prudent pediatric patients, especially CSF shunt patients [3]. For this reason, pediatric neurosurgeons have made considerable efforts to study and combat shunt-related diseases. Research on non-shunt neurological traumatic injuries in pediatric patients has not been as intensive. While various reviews have proposed strategies to reduce the risk of repetitive strain injuries in neurosurgery, including the use of double gloves, anti-infective prophylaxis and laminar flow wind circulation, there are still many opportunities to study and update additional measures to further reduce the risk of repetitive strain injuries, especially in non-shunt medical procedures. There is insufficient information on public rates of post-traumatic stress injuries in non-bypass systems [4]. Most research on SSI after pediatric neurosurgical methods is single-objective, single-technique focused examinations. Hence, a nationally approved clinical information base, containing provisional patient information, could be useful in distinguishing public SSI rates and hazard factors of the various techniques. The American College of Surgeons' National Surgical Quality Improvement Program database contains clinical patient data collected prospectively through prepared patient information summaries, with 82% of

the database requiring development at 30 days, providing very good information for such analysis [5].

METHODOLOGY:

The CSA-NSQIP Pediatrics (NSQIP-P) is a clinical information base for patients, with 50 children's clinics in 2012, 56 medical clinics in 2013 and 64 emergency clinics in 2014. This dataset is maintained and maintained by large pediatric medical procedure administrations. Cases including patients 18 years of age or older established at the time of the file system, injuries and transplants are excluded from NSQIP-P information collection. Our current research was conducted at Services Hospital, Lahore from May 2019 to April 2020. Each NSQIP site has a summary of information prepared and guaranteed by CHA. The rates of discrepancies between the various stakeholders are approximately 3% according to a review by the ACS, while well below the 5% rate of discrepancy considered "worthy" by the ACS. Past reviews have demonstrated that the NSQIP-P is an exceptionally robust collection of clinical information, with 92.6% of development asserted at 30 days¹¹. Studies exploring the NSQIP-P for information reliability found that satisfaction with the assortment of information for all factors was greater than 97% with 96% unshakeable quality in the initial phases of program implementation. Compared to authoritative information collections, such as the national inpatient sample that relies heavily on ICD-9 coding for accuracy, the NSQIP informational index is more tactile and explicit for detailed clinical information, such as greyness and mortality. The information in the NSQIP-P is more sensitive for taking PHI than data on claims and markers of nosocomial diseases. The Children of Alabama (COA) Pediatric Neurosurgical Disease Information Base was created through an audit of clinical records to determine risk factors for SSI. Pediatric neurosurgical techniques from January 2009 to March 2012 at COA were selected for the first collection of information. The COA is a high-volume, tertiary consideration emergency clinic serving a multi-state area in the southeastern United States. Both 30-day and 90-day ISO information was collected, with a minimum of 90 days for all patients.

Figure 1:

1 Cohort selection from the 2012–2014 NSQIP-P data set. Trauma cases (e.g., hematoma evacuations) are excluded a priori.

Table 1:

TABLE 1. Thirty-day SSIs by general procedure category (unadjusted univariate analysis)

Procedure Category	NSQIP-P				COA			
	No. of Procedures (% of total)	No. of SSIs (%)	OR (95% CI)	p Value	No. of Procedures (% of total)	No. of SSIs (%)	OR (95% CI)	p Value
Spine	2879 (31)	101 (3.5)	1.519 (1.176–1.963)	0.002	283 (26)	14 (4.9)	1.888 (0.952–3.742)	0.079
Craniotomy for neoplasm	2434 (26)	60 (2.5)	0.883 (0.658–1.184)	0.424	165 (15)	5 (3.0)	0.914 (0.350–2.386)	0.855
Chiari decompression	1748 (19)	33 (1.9)	0.647 (0.447–0.937)	0.021	84 (8)	0 (0)	NA	
Craniosynostosis/craniofacial	980 (11)	15 (1.5)	0.532 (0.314–0.901)	0.016	46 (4)	1 (2.2)	0.649 (0.087–4.843)	0.671
MMC closure	368 (4)	16 (4.3)	1.681 (1.002–2.821)	0.068	48 (4)	3 (6.3)	2.065 (0.610–6.987)	0.203
Epilepsy*	208 (2)	7 (3.4)	1.262 (0.588–2.711)	0.513	256 (23)	8 (3.1)	0.944 (0.425–2.097)	0.887
Skin lesion	136 (2)	1 (0.7)	0.264 (0.037–1.895)	0.276	70 (6)	1 (1.4)	0.413 (0.056–3.062)	0.723
Other†	543 (6)	18 (3.3)	1.254 (0.770–2.041)	0.340	171 (14)	4 (2.6)	0.782 (0.273–2.244)	0.808
Total	9296	251 (2.7)			1103	36 (3.3)		

NA = not available.

Odds ratios are with respect to development of any SSI compared to all other procedures not in respective category. Statistical tests were performed using the chi-square test and Fisher exact test where appropriate. Boldface type indicates statistical significance ($p < 0.05$).

* Data on epilepsy operations were not available for 2012–2013; NSQIP only has epilepsy procedure data for 2014. See Fig. 1 for more detailed procedural categorization by CPT code.

† The majority of procedures in "Other" category are baclofen pump placement/removal procedures (> 80% of total).

RESULTS:

The NSQIP-P has distinguished 9299 non-diversion neurosurgical techniques performed on pediatric patients between 2012 and 2014. A total of 2597 non-

diversion neurosurgical systems from 53 pediatric emergency clinics were distinguished in 2012, 3015 methods from 58 pediatric clinics in 2013, and 3689 strategies from 64 pediatric emergency clinics in 2014.

The overall rate of ISO at 30 days was 2.7% (n = 251). There was no great contrast between the rates of ISOs each year during the 2012-2014 period (Fig. 2). ISOs occurred 14.6 ± 6.8 days after surgery (mean $\pm$ standard deviation). The chances of a 30-day ISO in the NSQIP-P companion are shown in Fig. 3A. A total of 1108 no-lead systems performed by pediatric neurosurgeons between January 2009 and March 2012 were recognized in the COA institutional information. The overall 30-day ISO rate was 4.4% (n = 36, p = 0.326 compared to the 30-day ISO rate of NSQIP-P).

The overall 90-day ISO rate was 4.8%. ISO occurred 15.9 ± 8.4 days (mean $\pm$ standard deviation) post-operatively for 30-day contamination data collection, while ISO occurred 21.7 ± 17.6 days post-operatively for 90-day illness data collection. Figures 3B and C present separate information on the ideal timeliness of an ISO at 30 days and 90 days. Half of the COA 30-day SSIs were first refined from the injury, 37% from CSF, 7% from blood, and the remaining positive societies were from abscesses or different locations.

Figure 2:

Table 2:

Parameter	NSQIP-P				COA			
	Overall	SSI	OR (95% CI)	p Value	Overall	SSI	OR (95% CI)	p Value
Age in yrs, mean	7.0 $\pm$ 5.7	6.1 $\pm$ 5.6	0.971* (0.949–0.994)	0.013	7.9 $\pm$ 6.3	6.4 $\pm$ 5.5	0.957* (0.905–1.013)	0.132
Neonate	417 (4.5)	19 (4.6)	1.779 (1.103–2.871)	0.028	—	—	—	—
Sex								
Male	4863 (52.3)	115 (2.4)	Ref	—	578 (52.4)	18 (3.1)	Ref	—
Female	4433 (47.7)	136 (3.1)	1.307 (1.016–1.681)	0.040	525 (47.6)	18 (3.4)	1.105 (0.569–2.146)	0.769
Race								
White	7121 (76.6)	187 (2.6)	Ref	—	768 (69.6)	23 (3.0)	Ref	—
Black	852 (9.2)	25 (2.9)	1.121 (0.734–1.712)	0.597	263 (23.8)	11 (4.2)	1.414 (0.680–2.941)	0.354
Asian	220 (2.4)	9 (4.1)	1.582 (0.799–3.130)	0.188	11 (1.0)	0 (0)	NA	—
Pacific Islander	27 (0.3)	1 (3.7)	1.426 (0.193–10.565)	0.728	—	—	—	—
Native American	46 (0.5)	1 (2.2)	0.824 (0.113–6.010)	0.824	—	—	—	—
Unknown/NA	1030 (11.1)	28 (2.7)	1.036 (0.693–1.550)	0.863	2 (0.2)	0 (0)	NA	—
Hispanic	—	—	—	—	54 (4.9)	2 (3.7)	1.246 (0.286–5.429)	0.770
Biracial	—	—	—	—	5 (0.5)	0 (0)	NA	—
Insurance status								
Private	—	—	—	—	502 (45.5)	12 (2.4)	Ref	—
Public	—	—	—	—	555 (50.3)	24 (4.3)	1.857 (0.919–3.753)	0.085
Private w/ secondary public	—	—	—	—	3 (0.3)	0 (0)	NA	—
Self pay	—	—	—	—	37 (3.4)	0 (0)	NA	—
Unknown	—	—	—	—	6 (0.5)	0 (0)	NA	—
Weeks of gestation								
≥ 37	7233 (77.8)	195 (2.7)	Ref	—	848 (76.9)	27 (3.2)	Ref	—
33–36	710 (7.6)	13 (1.8)	0.785 (0.108–5.718)	0.811	105 (9.5)	3 (2.9)	0.894 (0.267–3.000)	0.857
29–32	798 (8.6)	26 (3.3)	1.578 (0.766–3.248)	0.216	63 (5.7)	4 (6.3)	2.062 (0.734–6.224)	0.190
25–28	317 (3.4)	8 (2.5)	0.934 (0.457–1.912)	0.853	40 (3.6)	1 (2.5)	0.780 (0.103–5.887)	0.809
≤ 24	191 (2.1)	8 (4.2)	1.216 (0.802–1.842)	0.358	7 (0.6)	0 (0)	NA	—
Unknown	47 (0.5)	1 (0.4)	0.673 (0.382–1.187)	0.171	40 (3.6)	1 (2.5)	0.780 (0.103–5.887)	0.809

Ref = reference.

Data are presented as number of cases (%) unless otherwise indicated. Continuous variables are expressed as mean $\pm$ SD. Statistical tests were performed using the Student t-test, chi-square test, and Fisher exact test where appropriate. Boldface type indicates statistical significance (p < 0.05).

* Per year increase.

Table 3:

Variable	Adjusted OR	95% CI	p Value
NSQIP-P parameters			
Postop pneumonia*	4.761	1.269–17.857	0.021
Immune disease or immunosuppressant use	3.671	1.371–9.827	0.010
Cerebral palsy	2.835	1.463–5.494	0.002
Emergency operation	1.843	1.011–3.360	0.046
Spine procedure	1.673	1.036–2.702	0.035
Acquired CNS abnormality	1.620	1.085–2.420	0.018
Female sex	1.475	1.062–2.049	0.021
COA parameters			
Clean-contaminated wound class	3.887	1.354–11.153	0.012
Public insurance	1.966	0.957–4.041	0.066
Spine procedure	1.982	0.955–4.114	0.066

Boldface type indicates statistical significance ($p < 0.05$).

* Cases in which SSI occurred before or concurrent with postoperative pneumonia were excluded from this variable analysis.

DISCUSSION:

We distinguished 30-day contamination rates and hazard factors for SSIs by following pediatric neurosurgical strategies without derivation, using a public clinical information base and an institutional, explicit neurosurgical information base [6]. Our results show that the NSQIP-P SSI rates across the country are similar to those at our own institution. Spine techniques, craniotomies and epilepsy systems had the highest ISO rates in both sets of data [7]. The main findings of this review are that the NSQIP-P is a sensitive device for epidemiological information on the recurrence of SSIs, the SSI tries to predict the use of factors given by the NSQIP informational index and a collection of explicit institutional information on neurosurgery, and the hazard factors distinguished in the two collections of information are generally not modifiable [8]. ISS rates have changed fundamentally between the different types of methodology, while no individual strategy has had an ISS rate greater than

12%. When thinking about the classifications of the methodology, the backbone techniques were well on their way to being linked to the classifieds. Laminectomies were particularly dangerous for small processors, with three of the top seven strategies based on the rate of these companies [9]. Craniotomies for midline or subtotal hemispherectomy, EEG extraction of the epileptogenous center during medical intervention, and craniopharyngioma extraction were also moderately more dangerous for SSIs; these are normally complicated strategies with long usable periods and enormous hidden co-morbidity of the patient. The overall rarity of each of the above-mentioned systems may play a role in the likelihood of SSI progression [10].

CONCLUSION:

We distinguished the rates and risk factors of SSIs at 30 days after pediatric neurosurgery without shunt, using a public information database and an

institutional data set. The NSQIP-P information and that of a solitary foundation were comparable in many respects. Pediatric patients undergoing spinal medical procedures, craniotomy for epilepsy and MMC conclusion systems are particularly at risk for SSI. Postoperative pneumonia, safe use of disease/immunosuppressant, cerebral palsy, seizure activity, technical class of the spine, CNS irregularity achieved, and female gender are all dangers of ISS freely spread in the NSQIP-P, while the self-injury-polluted injury pattern autonomously anticipated ISS in information from a solitary community.

REFERENCES:

1. Kulaylat AN, Engbrecht BW, Rocourt DV, Rinaldi JM, Santos MC, Cilley RE, et al. Measuring surgical site infections in children: comparing clinical, electronic, and administrative data. *J Am Coll Surg.* 2016; 222:823–830. [PubMed: 27010586]
2. Kulkarni AV, Drake JM, Lamberti-Pasculli M. Cerebrospinal fluid shunt infection: a prospective study of risk factors. *J Neurosurg.* 2001; 94:195–201. [PubMed: 11213954]
3. Lam S, Pan IW, Jea A, Luerssen TG. Bridging the gap between administrative data and clinical observations. *J Neurosurg Pediatr.* 2016; 17:763–764. [PubMed: 26824596]
4. Lejus C, Dumont R, Gall CL, Guillaud C, Guen CG, Leclair MD, et al. A preoperative stay in an intensive care unit is associated with an increased risk of surgical site infection in neonates. *J Pediatr Surg.* 2013; 48:1503–1508. [PubMed: 23895963]
5. Lieber BA, Appelboom G, Taylor BE, Lowy FD, Bruce EM, Sonabend AM, et al. Preoperative chemotherapy and corticosteroids: independent predictors of cranial surgical-site infections. *J Neurosurg.* 2016; 125:187–195. [PubMed: 26544775]
6. Lieber B, Han B, Strom RG, Mullin J, Frempong-Boadu AK, Agarwal N, et al. Preoperative predictors of spinal infection within the National Surgical Quality Inpatient Database. *World Neurosurg.* 2016; 89:517–524. [PubMed: 26748173]
7. Mangram AJ, Horan TC, Pearson ML, Silver LC, Jarvis WR. Guideline for prevention of surgical site infection, 1999. *Am J Infect Control.* 1999; 27:96–134.
8. McCutcheon BA, Ubl DS, Babu M, Maloney P, Murphy M, Kerezoudis P, et al. Predictors of surgical site infection following craniotomy for intracranial neoplasms: an analysis of prospectively collected data in the American College of Surgeons National Surgical Quality Improvement Program database. *World Neurosurg.* 2016; 88:350–358. [PubMed: 26743384]
9. Meng F, Cao J, Meng X. Risk factors for surgical site infection following pediatric spinal deformity surgery: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Childs Nerv Syst.* 2015; 31:521–527. [PubMed: 25707483]
10. Mioton LM, Jordan SW, Hanwright PJ, Bilimoria KY, Kim JY. The relationship between preoperative wound classification and postoperative infection: a multi-institutional analysis of 15,289 patients. *Arch Plast Surg.* 2013; 40:522–529. [PubMed: 24086804]